
TAX SHIELD ON EFFECTIVE TAX RATE AND EARNINGS MANAGEMENT OF NIGERIAN DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS

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Abstract: *This study examined corporate tax shield and earnings management of Nigerian deposit money banks, using effective tax rate as the independent variable and TACC for dependent variable. Ex post facto research design was employed for the study. A sample of thirteen (13) banks was used for the study. Data were extracted from annual reports and accounts of the sampled banks. Regression analysis, the study revealed that effective tax rate has negative and insignificant effect on earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. However, the study conclude that tax shield of effective tax rate has no significant effect on earning management in Nigerian banks. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the use of effective tax rate by management to generate growth should be discouraged.*

Keywords: *Tax shield, Effective tax rate and Earnings management.*

Introduction

Earnings management is the management's action to window dress the real image of the business to misrepresent or attract the eyes of the users. It is a complex issue dealing with the management manipulation of profits with a view to showing the company financial performance according to the ideas of the company management (Gregova, Simreka, Michalkova & Svabova, 2021). Earnings management can also be seen as the regulation of profit to reflect the goals of management, or stakeholders or special purpose income settings. It involves all the efforts of management to maintain a firm's fluctuations in earnings at a level that is considered normal according to sound accounting and management practices (Paohan, 2019). It is the practice of managerial actions that are reflected in a company's financial reports either to give the impression of smooth periodic or annual earnings, to show high profits in a given year towards achieving lowered reported earnings in the future; or to show low profit in a given year so that in future years reported profits will be higher (Gills, Biger, Mand, & Mathur, 2021). It is the use of accounting techniques to produce financial statements that present an overly positive view of a company's business activities and financial position (Paohan, 2019).

In other words, shareholders' wealth expropriation may not be the only incentive for earnings management. Some studies argued that, managers and controlling owners have incentives to manage

reported earnings to mask true firm performance (Leuza, Nanda, & Wysocki, 2021) to conceal their private control benefits from outsiders, to manipulating earnings to depict good performance, to meet bonus targets (Bartov, Gul, & Tsui, 2019), and to meet the demands of their investors and creditors.

In some cases, management uses various accounting methods to convey private information to financial report readers: management of earnings may mislead stakeholders about the true financial performance of the company. One of such motivations is to provide good news to corporate boards by showing good results in a certain period (Paohan, 2019). Managers also tend to manipulate earnings to surprise investors, improve share price, and lower debt costs (Gills, et al, 2021). This can be done through: income smoothing, window dressing and secret reserves, off statement of financial position financing, pooling among others (Paohan, 2019).

Though there is inconsistency in the results of previous studies, these studies were carried out mainly in foreign countries, such as; Bahrain, Egypt, Jordan, Kuwait, Morocco, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Tunisia, United Arab Emirates and U.S. only very few of these studies were on Nigeria. Against this backdrop, this study was intended to fill the created gap through the various tax shield mechanism such as the medical expenses, charity donations, amortization, and depreciation and how they affect earnings management in the deposit money bank (DMB) in Nigeria. The DMB were chosen because of the strategic role of this sector to the Nigerian economy. This study therefore, evaluates the effect of effective tax rate on earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Corporate Tax Shield

Corporate tax shield refer to the reduction in income taxes that a corporation enjoys due to certain deductible expenses, such as interest payments on debt. A tax shield is the deliberate use of taxable expenses to offset taxable income (Paohan, 2019). Tax shield lowers tax bills, which is one of the major reasons why taxpayers, whether individuals or corporations, spend a considerable amount of time determining which deduction and credits they qualify for each year. This can lower the effective tax rate of a business or individual. The value of a tax shield is calculated as the amount of the taxable expense, multiplied by the tax rate. Thus, if the tax rate is 35%, and the business has ₦1,000 of interest expense, the tax shield value of the interest expense is ₦350.

Effective Tax Rate

The effective tax rate (ETR) is the average taxation rate for a corporation or individual. The effective tax rate for individuals is the average rate at which their earned income is taxed, and the effective tax rate for a corporation is the average rate at which its pre-tax profits are taxed (Jon, 2012). The effective tax rate is the average rate at which an individual is taxed on earned income, or the average rate at which a corporation is taxed on pre-tax profits.

ETR has been used in prior studies (Rego, 2003; Khaoula and Ayed, 2013; and, Seyrama and Holy, 2014), to measure a reflection of tax planning that decreases a firm's tax liability without necessarily

decreasing its accounting income. Corporate ETR basically assesses the tax performance of firms (Rego, 2003). Thus, it is the best measure to evaluate the actual corporate tax burdens. ETR is a commonly used measure of a firm's tax burden. ETR provides a basic summary statistic of tax performance which describes the amount of taxes paid by a company relative to its profit before tax. This measure reflects aggressive tax planning through permanent book tax differences, (Khaoula & Ayed, 2013). The ETR is computed as a proportion of tax paid to profit before tax.

The effective tax rate for a corporation is the average rate at which its pre-tax profits are taxed. An individual's effective tax rate is calculated by dividing total tax expense by taxable income. Rego (2003) interpreted ETR as a measure of the effectiveness of tax planning in which taxes currently payable are compared with what would be apparent from the income figure in the financial statements. Therefore, effective tax rates are often utilized as a measure of effective tax planning among companies (Zimmerman, 1983). Hence, average ETR is the appropriate measure for tax avoidance since it shows that the impact it has on incentives, income shifting and tax avoidance (Rego, 2003).

Generally, ETR is defined as the ratio of taxes to profit from existing investments (Zimmerman, 1983). The issue about measuring ETR relates to which taxes to include as the numerator and how to measure profit as the denominator. Several groups of ETR studies have measured ETR differently. Hanlon and Shevlin (2001) discussed the calculation of ETR used by the Government Accounting Office (GAO). The GAO uses the ratio of current portion of tax expense to net income. ETR is usually measured by dividing tax liability by profit.

ETR is measured as the ratio of income taxes currently payable to pre-tax accounting income. Rego (2003) claims that firms that avoid income taxes by reducing their income tax payable while maintaining their accounting income will have lower ETR, thus making ETR a reasonable measure of tax avoidance. Guenther (2014) stated that researchers in accounting and finance have used effective tax rate as a measure of corporate tax avoidance in empirical research.

Earnings Management

The concept of earnings management stems from the trade-off between relevance and reliability in financial reporting (Ofurum, Okoye, & Ezejiofor, 2021). Sundvik (2017) reported that highly reliable financial reports solely include realized cash flows, whereas highly relevant reports are concerned with the current value of expected future cash flows. Since accounting rules and legislation demand both relevance and reliability in proportion, financial reporting is therefore associated with certain elements of discretion and managerial judgment. Academic accounting literature provides many definitions of the term earnings management. Derived from the opportunistic use of discretion in financial reporting, the early literature defined the notion of earnings management as "a purposeful intervention in the external financial reporting process, with the intent of obtaining some private gain" (Schipper, 1989). Here, earnings management is viewed through an opportunistic lens.

In line with Walker (2013) had two views on earnings management by noting the opportunistic behavior perspective as well as an information perspective. From the information viewpoint, earnings management occurs when the management wants to communicate or signal their private expectations about future cash flows to external parties. The goal of informative earnings management is to improve the relevance of the financial reporting and enhance the usefulness of the financial statement information. This is something that would increase value, in contrast to the opportunistic standpoint whereby managers act out of self-interest and thus, decrease value through their actions. Earnings management is frequently also used as an indicator for financial reporting quality or earnings quality in the financial accounting literature, where more absolute earnings management is equal to lower quality earnings and where higher quality is preferred (Dechow, Ge, & Schrand 2010).

Empirical Reviews

Oranefo (2022) investigated the effect of effective tax rate on cash flow of manufacturing firms in Nigeria and Ghana. *Ex Post Facto* research design was employed. A sample of consumer manufacturing firms was used and data for the study were extracted from annual accounts of the sampled firms of both countries, and the hypotheses were tested after the analysis using Ordinary Least Square analysis. The result revealed that the sampled firms in Nigeria have a favourable impact on cash flow while that of Ghanaian has not, but their impact was not statistically significant at the 5% level of significance. Ndum (2022) assessed the effect of corporate tax avoidance on earnings management in Nigerian deposit money banks from 2010 to 2020. *Ex- post facto* research design was employed. Nine deposit money banks with international authorization constitute the sample size of the study. The hypotheses were tested and Ordinary Least Square with the aid of E-View 9.0 used to arrive at a logical conclusion. The study revealed that amortization has significant effect on Earnings Management of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Ofurum, Okoye, and Ezejiofor (2021) examined corporate tax shield and earnings management: An empirical analysis of commercial banks in Nigeria. Their study adopted *ex-post facto* research design. 13 commercial banks with international authorization constituted the sample size of the study. Ordinary Least Square was used for the analysis. Findings revealed that medical expenses and amortization have a positive relationship with and significant effect on earnings management of commercial banks in Nigeria. In another development, Ofurum and Okoye (2021) evaluated the effect of tax shield on earnings management in Nigeria commercial banks from 2010 to 2019. The study used charity donations as an independent variable while earnings management as a dependent variable. *Ex-post facto* research design was adopted for the study. Purposive sampling was employed to arrival at 13 commercial banks which consists the sample size of the study. Ordinary Least Square was employed and the hypotheses were tested. The results show that charity donations have not significantly affected earnings management of commercial banks in Nigeria. Prabowo, Winarna, Aryani, Falikhatun, and Gantjowati (2020) assessed debt and earnings management in Indonesia: An issue of free cash-flow or covenant.

Analysis was based on a sample set consisting of 497 firms engaging in manufacturing operations listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange during the period of 2009 to 2014. The results revealed that corporate debt is an important determinant of earnings management as it was statistically significant. Further tests revealed that the interaction between liquidity and specification of corporate debt shapes different pattern of the directions of earnings management. Purnama and Nurdiniah (2019) examined profitability, firm size, and earnings management: The moderating effect of managerial ownership. The study sought to know: if a company size influence profit; whether managerial ownership can afford to strengthen or weaken the influence of the size of the company towards profit. Population and sample population used in this research was the company's food and beverages sector in Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) in between 2012-2016. Purposive sampling technique was adopted. Findings revealed that profitability has a positive relationship with and earnings management while firm size negatively affected earnings management. Managerial ownership is found not to be moderating variable on the profitability, firm size and earnings management. Shazad (2017) carried out a study on earning management strategies of leveraged family and non-family controlled firms: empirical evidence. The study examined whether the choices of real and accrual base earning management of family and non-family firms are associated with the leverage. Also they investigated the role of family control on the relation of leverage with real and accrual base earning management. All publicly listed companies (excluding finance stocks) listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange over the period 2007-2014 are included in the population. However, a total number of 95 companies were randomly selected as a sample. Hence, the sample size is 760 firms/year. The choice of timeframe for the study was driven by a series of changes in the accounting standards that took place in 2006 when Pakistan switched from GAAP to IFRS. The *hypotheses* were tested and Feasible Generalized Least Square Regression (FGLS) estimation approach was used. It was discovered that leverage is positively associated with real earning management. Furthermore, leveraged firm is negatively associated with accrual base earning management due to higher litigation risk of accrual based earning management. Moreover, the impact of leverage on real and accrual earning management is stronger for family controlled businesses than non-family controlled businesses. Francisco, Elena, and Antonio, (2012) investigated size and other determinants of corporate effective tax rates in US listed companies. The study noted the determinants of corporate Effective Tax Rates (ETR) based on a panel of listed US companies over the period 1992-2009 (Compustat), with a special focus on firm size. They also considered the economic and financial structure of the firms, as well as profitability. The results indicated a non-linear relation between size and ETR, with similar relationships also found for debt and capital intensity.

Methodology

Ex-post facto research design was adopted for the study, hence, the researcher does not have direct control of the independent variables because their manifestation have already occurred or manipulated.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of twenty one (21) deposit money banks quoted on the Nigeria Exchange group from 2014-2023.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The researchers used purposive sampling technique to select thirteen (13) quoted deposit money bank on the Nigeria Exchange Group, out of the twenty one banks stated as population of this study. The choice of these banks was based on the availability of data that covered the period under study.

Sources of Data Collection

To obtain reliable information that helped in this study to ensure the effectiveness of the study in question, data were collected from only secondary sources. The data were extracted from the annual reports and audited accounts of the banks under study from 2013 to 2023.

Model Specification

The model for this study was adapted from the study of Ofurum, Okoye, and Ezejiofor (2021) which was modified to suit the variables under study. The adapted model is presented as thus: $EAMGT = f(MDE, CHD, AMT, \text{ and } DEP)$.

In the course of modifying the model a variable such as Effective Tax Rate (ETR) was added to make the model conformed to the earlier stated specific objectives. Thereafter the newly modified model of this study is presented in functional form as stated below.

$EAMGT = f(ETR, MDE, CHD, AMT, DEP) \dots \dots \dots \text{Model}_1$

The econometric form of the model is stated in the equation below.

$$EMG_{it} = \beta_1 ETR_{it} + \sum_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{Eqn 1}$$

Where: EMG = Earnings Management

ETR = Effective Tax Rate

β_1 = Constant/Intercepts

β_1 –Regression Coefficient

\sum = Error Term

i = Cross section

t = Time Period

Measuring Dependent Variable (Earnings Management)

This study employed the modified Jones's model (Dechow et al., 1995) to measure the level of earnings management or discretionary accruals (DTAC). This model employed total accruals (TAC)

that are classified as discretionary components (DTAC) and non-discretionary components (NDTAC).

Thus, defined as follows:

$$TAC = NDTAC + DTAC$$

Where:

TAC = Total accrual period t

NDTAC = Value of non-discretionary accruals

DTAC = Discretionary accrual

Method of Data Analysis

The study utilized descriptive statistics and simple regression analysis. Other diagnostic tests were also conducted out, test like Johansen co-integration rank test and pairwise granger causality test.

Decision rule

The study's hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance. In view of that, when the p-statistics is less than 0.05, the null hypotheses is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Data Analysis and Results

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics provides evidence on the mean distribution, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, median and the count of the data collected which span from 2014 to 2023.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	TACC	ETR
Mean	-2.70E+08	0.004351
Median	-3.79E+08	0.002261
Maximum	4.14E+09	0.016430
Minimum	-5.50E+09	-0.002040
Std. Dev.	3.09E+09	0.005762
Skewness	-0.164774	0.878249
Kurtosis	2.004286	2.841274
Jarque-Bera	0.458353	1.296033
Probability	0.795188	0.523082
Sum	-2.70E+09	0.043510
Sum Sq. Dev.	8.59E+19	0.000299
Observations	26	26

Source: E-view 9 Output

Table 1 indicates the mean (average) for each of the variables, their maximum values, minimum values, standard deviation and Jarque-Bera (JB) statistics (normality test).

The result revealed average over the ten (10) year period (2014-2023), the sampled quoted banks in Nigeria were characterized by negative average TACC (-2.70E+08). The study shows that the average

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effective tax rate (ETR) value is 0.004351 with maximum value of 0.016430 and minimum value of -0.002040. Medical expenses (MDE) value over the period was 374481.4; the maximum value was 472758.7 while the minimum stood at 252258.0.

From Table 1 above, the Jarque-Bera (JB) which test for normality or the existence of outlier or extreme values among the variables shows that all our variables are normally distributed and significant at 5% level and the result could be generalized. This also implies that a least square regression can be used to estimate the regression models.

Test of Hypothesis

In order to examine the effect of TACC on the variable (ETR) and to also test the formulated hypotheses, a regression analysis was used in table 2 below.

Table 2: The Regression Analysis Result

Dependent Variable: TACC

Method: Least Squares

Date: 06/20/25 Time: 11:43

Sample: 2014 2023

Included observations: 26

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-9.67E+09	2.50E+09	-3.865690	0.0181
ETR	-2.11E+11	1.07E+11	-1.968798	0.1203
R-squared	0.940769	Mean dependent var		2.70E+08
Adjusted R-squared	0.866731	S.D. dependent var		3.09E+09
S.E. of regression	1.13E+09	Akaike info criterion		44.80861
Sum squared resid	5.09E+18	Schwarz criterion		44.99016
Log likelihood	-218.0431	Hannan-Quinn criter.		44.60945
F-statistic	12.70653	Durbin-Watson stat		1.821326
Prob(F-statistic)	0.014450			

Table 2 shows that regression analysis was conducted to test the effect between Tax shield (effective tax) and earnings management. The result revealed that effective tax rate has negative and no significant effect on earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria. From the findings in the Table 2, the value of adjusted R squared was 0.87. This implies that only 87% changes in earnings management of banks could be accounted for by independent variable; ETR, while 13% was explained by unknown variables that were not included in the model.

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 1.821326 suggests that the model does not contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the regression is equal to 12.70653 and the associated F-statistical probability is equal to 0.014, so the alternative hypothesis was accepted and the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Effective tax rate has not significantly affected earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

The probability of the slope coefficients indicate that; P-value = 0.1203 > 0.05). The co-efficient value of; $\beta_1 = -2.110$; $t = -1.969$ for TAC implies that effective tax rate is negatively related to earnings management, and also not statistically significant at 5%.

Decision

Since the P-value of 0.1203 is higher than the critical value of 5% (0.05), then, it would be upheld that effective tax rate has not significantly influenced earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria at 5% level of significance, thus, H₀ is preferred to H₁.

From the findings in hypothesis one, the probability of the slope coefficients indicate that; P-value = 0.1203 > 0.05). The co-efficient value of; $\beta_1 = -2.110$; $t = -1.969$ for TAC implies that effective tax rate is negatively related to earnings management, and also not statistically significant at 5%. The result from the findings are in congruence with Amidu and Yorke (2017); Amidu, Kwakye, Ayunku and Uzochukwu (2020); Foroozian and Gaskari (2016).

Conclusion

This study examined corporate tax shield and earnings management using effective tax rate as the independent variable and TACC for dependent variable. Regression analysis, the study revealed that effective tax rate has negative and insignificant effect on earnings management of deposit money banks in Nigeria at 5% level of significance. However, the study conclude that tax shield of effective tax rate has no significant effect on earning management in Nigerian banks. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the use of effective tax rate by management to generate growth should be discouraged.

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